

THE ROLE OF DERMATOPHAGOID MITES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ALLERGIC RHINITIS IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Allergic diseases modern medicine serious problem is considered to WHO according to allergic diseases spreading common diseases between the third place occupied Epidemiological to the results according to of the population approx 10-30 percentage allergy with suffers. 20 from after to allergies played the sick the number 50% up to enough. One series studies through allergic diseases landface of the population 25 percentage organize to doanddifferent countrie sillness level from each other much difference to dowas determined. breathgetto allergens sensitivity breath get allergiesof formation main from the factorsis one. Cockroaches- home powder contentallergen components between important role who plays are aeroallergens. Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus and Dermatophagoides farinae residence buildings of acarofauna 90% part organize enough.

Keywords: Allergic rhinitis, dermatophagoides pteronyssinus, dermatophagoides farinae, bronchial asthma.

PRIORITY

Allergic rhinitis is one of the most urgent global problems of medicine. According to medical statistics, mites are the etiological factor in two-thirds of children suffering

from bronchial asthma. The house dust mite or dust mite belongs to the arachnid class of synanthropic mites. These mites are called dermatophagoid mites. House dust parasites make up 62% of the country. Although dust can contain more than 150, however, 2 types of dermatophagoids are more dominant in distribution. These are *Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus*, *Dermatophagoides farinae*. Mites make up the main part of the air that the patient breathes. They are found on pillows, carpets, soft furniture and paper. Mites and their vital products cause allergic rhinitis and atopic dermatitis despite their very small size. Allergic rhinitis caused by dermatophagoids occurs differently in different regions of our country.

THE GOAL

Analysis of specific characteristics of allergic rhinitis with dermatophagoid (*Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus* and *Dermatophagoides farinae*) etiology. Implementation of the statistical analysis of the meeting rate in the conditions of Uzbekistan. To study the dependence of the reasons on climatic conditions.

METHOD AND MATERIAL OF SCIENTIFIC INVESTIGATION

It is planned to conduct clinical and laboratory examinations in order to study the clinical features of the disease and to determine the level of occurrence of *Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus* and *Dermatophagoides farinae* mites in 60 patients aged 7-40 years who have applied to the Republican Specialized-Scientific Allergology Center from different regions. .

RESULTS AND ANALYSES

Scientific research was conducted at the Republican scientific specialized center of allergology. The investigation was conducted during the years 2019-2022, and 60 patients aged 7 to 40 years with pollinosis were studied. In accordance with the tasks, all patients whose data were collected retrospectively and diagnosed with allergic rhinitis-permanent type were distributed across all regions and studied according to 2 types of dermatophagoid mites.

Table

He applied to the republican scientific specialized allergology center **Allergic rhinitis, persistent type**, etiological cause 2 types of dermatophagoid mites distribution according to

Address	Total N=70	
	Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus	Dermatophagoides farinae
Tashkent city	4	1
Tashkent region	4	1
Andijan region	3	2
Fergana region	4	1
Namangan region	3	2
Sirdarya region	4	1
Jizzakh region	2	3
Samarkand region	2	3
Kashkadarya region	2	3
Surkhandarya region	1	4
Bukhara region	2	3
Navoi region	3	2
Khorezm region	1	4
Republic of Karakalpakstan	2	3

The percentage distribution of patients from different regions and cities of the Republic who applied to the Allergology Center of the Republic and were diagnosed with allergic rhinitis of permanent type (dermatophagoid etiology) is as follows:

Tashkent city

(Der. p – 80%, Der.f – 20%)

The prevalence of dermatophagoides pteronyssinus was found to be high in this region.

Tashkent region

(Der. p – 80%, Der.f – 20%)

The prevalence of dermatophagoides pteronyssinus was found to be high in this region

Andijan region

(Der. p – 60%, Der. f – 40%)

In this region, the prevalence of dermatophagoides pteronyssinus was found to be relatively high

Fergana region

(Der. p – 80%, Der.f – 20%)

In this region, the prevalence of dermatophagoides pteronyssinus was found to be relatively high

Namangan region

(Der. p – 60%, Der. f – 40%)

In this region, the prevalence of dermatophagoides pteronyssinus was found to be relatively high

Sirdarya region

(Der. p – 80%, Der.f – 20%)

In this region, the prevalence of dermatophagoides pteronyssinus was found to be relatively high

Jizzakh region

(Der. p – 40%, Der. f – 60%)

The prevalence of dermatophagoides farinae was found to be relatively high in this region

Samarkand region
(Der. p – 40%, Der. f – 60%)

The prevalence of dermatophagoides farinae was found to be relatively high in this region

Kashkadarya region
(Der. p – 40%, Der. f – 60%)

The prevalence of dermatophagoides farinae was found to be relatively high in this region

Surkhandarya region

(Der. p – 40%, Der. f – 60%)

The prevalence of dermatophagoides farinae was found to be relatively high in this region

Bukhara region

(Der. p – 40%, Der. f – 60%)

The prevalence of dermatophagoides farinae was found to be relatively high in this region

Navoi region

(Der. p – 60%, Der. f – 40%)

In this region, the prevalence of dermatophagoides pteronyssinus was found to be relatively high

Khorezm region

(Der. p – 20%, Der.f – 80%)

The prevalence of dermatophagoides farinae was found to be relatively high in this region

Republic of Karakalpakstan

(Der. p – 40%, Der. f – 60%)

The prevalence of dermatophagoides farinae was found to be relatively high in this region

SUMMARY

According to the determined data, house dust mites were counted in the regions. It can be seen that the distribution of dermatophagoides farinae and dermatophagoides pteronyssinus is not uniform in different regions of the Republic. The spread of dermatophagoides farinae and dermatophagoides pteronyssinus in different regions of the republic was mainly manifested in regions with a dry and humid climate.

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